

1 **Characterization of Viruses in Phase III and Phase IIIb Trials (The Ring Study**
2 **and DREAM) of the Dapivirine Vaginal Ring for HIV-1 Infection Risk Reduction**

3

4 **Authors:**

5 John Steytler¹, Charles Craig², Elna van der Ryst³, Ben Van Baelen⁴, Jeremy
6 Nuttall⁵, Neliëtte van Niekerk¹, John Mellors⁶, Urvi Parikh⁶, and Carole Wallis⁷, for
7 The Ring Study and DREAM Study Teams.

8

9 **Affiliations:**

10 ¹ International Partnership for Microbicides South Africa NPC, Johannesburg, South
11 Africa

12 ² Research Virology Consulting Ltd, Cambridgeshire, United Kingdom

13 ³ Independent Consultant, Kent, United Kingdom

14 ⁴ BVB Clin Consult BVBA, Herent, Belgium

15 ⁵ International Partnership for Microbicides, Silver Spring, MD, USA

16 ⁶ Microbicide Trials Network Virology Core Laboratory, University of Pittsburgh,
17 Pittsburgh, PA, USA

18 ⁷ Bio-Analytical Research Corporation Laboratory (BARC-SA) and Lancet
19 Laboratories, Johannesburg, South Africa

20

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28 **Corresponding Author:**

29 John Steytler

30 International Partnership for Microbicides South Africa NPC

31 Woodlands Office Park, Building 16, 1st Floor, 20 Woodlands Drive, Woodmead,

32 Johannesburg, 2191, South Africa

33 Email: jsteytler@ipmglobal.org

34 Tel: +27 21 860 2358

35 Fax: +27 21 860 2311

36

37 **Alternate Corresponding Author:**

38 Neliëtte van Niekerk

39 International Partnership for Microbicides South Africa NPC

40 Woodlands Office Park, Building 16, 1st Floor, 20 Woodlands Drive, Woodmead,

41 Johannesburg, 2191, South Africa

42 Email: nvanniekerk@ipmglobal.org

43 Tel: +27 21 860 2316

44 Fax: +27 21 860 2311

45

46 **Summary of main point:**

47 HIV-1 NNRTI susceptibility analysis using population-based genotyping after

48 infection as well as Next Generation Sequencing and phenotypic susceptibility

49 analyses at seroconversion do not indicate any evidence of increased NNRTI

50 resistance-associated mutations or dapivirine susceptibility reduction after DVR use.

51 **Abstract**

52 **Background**

53 The Ring Study, a 2:1 randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled Phase III trial,
54 demonstrated 35.1% HIV-1 infection risk reduction among participants using the
55 Dapivirine Vaginal Ring-004 (DVR). An open-label extension trial, DREAM,
56 approximated a 62% risk reduction. The analysis of NNRTI resistance-associated
57 mutations (RAMs) and effects on viral susceptibility observed in these trials are
58 described.

59

60 **Methods**

61 Population-based genotyping was performed on plasma samples collected
62 longitudinally, and Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) and phenotypic susceptibility
63 testing was done on plasma collected at seroconversion. Retrospective HIV-1 RNA
64 testing was used to establish more accurately the time of infection.

65

66 **Results**

67 In The Ring Study, NNRTI RAMs were not observed in most viruses at
68 seroconversion (population-based genotyping: DVR: 71/84, 84.5%; placebo: 50/58,
69 86.2%). However, more E138A was found in the DVR group (E138A: DVR: 9/84,
70 10.7%; placebo: 2/58, 3.4%, $P=0.2$, Fisher's exact test). NGS detected one
71 additional mutation in each group (DVR: G190A; placebo: G190A and G190E).
72 Marginal dapivirine susceptibility reduction was found with NNRTI RAMs at
73 seroconversion (geometric mean fold-change [FC], range: DVR: 3.1, 1.3 – 5.1;
74 placebo: 5.8, 0.9 – 120). NNRTI RAMs were not emergent between first detectable
75 HIV-1 RNA and seroconversion when these visits differed (paired samples, mean

76 ring use: DVR: n=52, 35 days; placebo: n=26, 31 days). After stopping DVR, 2/63

77 viruses had emergent G190G/A or K103K/N with V106V/M at final study visit.

78 Resistance profiles from DREAM were consistent with The Ring Study.

79

80 **Conclusion**

81 DVR used for HIV-1 prevention showed little potential for selection of NNRTI

82 resistant variants.

83 **Introduction**

84 A silicone-matrix vaginal ring containing the diarylpyrimidine (DAPY) NNRTI,
85 dapivirine (Dapivirine Vaginal Ring-004: DVR), formulated to provide sustained
86 dapivirine release, demonstrated a statistically significant risk reduction for HIV-1
87 infection compared to placebo in The Ring Study (risk reduction: 35.1%, 95% CI:
88 9.1 – 53.6) and 62% risk reduction was observed based on statistical modelling in
89 DREAM (1,8). However, use of the DVR as part of the sub-Saharan African pre-
90 exposure prophylaxis strategy needs to consider the potential for dapivirine,
91 delivered using a vaginal ring, to promote NNRTI-resistant variant selection and
92 efficacy reduction for later NNRTI-based treatment regimens.

93

94 Dapivirine is chemically like the approved NNRTIs etravirine and rilpivirine, which
95 have high molecular flexibility to help retain potency against a wide range of drug-
96 resistant HIV-1 reverse transcriptases (RTs) (2). Vaginal delivery achieves high
97 dapivirine concentrations in vaginal fluid with very low systemic exposure (3). This is
98 expected to reduce the risk of transmission of wild-type virus and of viruses with
99 moderate NNRTI resistance, and to make selection of resistant virus in breakthrough
100 infection less likely (4).

101

102 NNRTI resistance-associated mutations (RAMs) K101E, E138K, K103N, K103S,
103 F227C and Y181C are associated with low-level dapivirine resistance in vitro (2- to
104 8 fold-change [FC]); L100I, L100V and M230L with intermediate resistance (8- to
105 20 FC) and K101P, Y181I, Y181V, Y188L and G190E with high-level resistance
106 (>20 FC) (5). In vitro selection of other NNRTI RAMs, L100I, V106I, E138K and
107 polymorphic accessory mutation V90I in wild-type subtype C viruses, the most

108 prevalent subtype in sub-Saharan Africa (6, 7), showed reduced susceptibility to
109 dapivirine.

110

111 We described previously the population-based genotypic findings at seroconversion
112 from The Ring Study Phase III trial (IPM 027, NCT01539226) (3) and the DREAM
113 Phase IIIb open-label extension trial (IPM 032, NCT02862171) (8). Here we extend
114 virologic assessments through the open-label stage of The Ring Study with a
115 longitudinal analysis of population-based genotyping and analyses using Next
116 Generation Sequencing (NGS) and phenotypic susceptibility assays in both trials.

117 **Methods**

118 ***Study Design and Participants***

119 The Ring Study was a multicenter, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled,
120 Phase III trial to assess the safety and efficacy of the DVR (3). Briefly, participants
121 were assigned in a 2:1 ratio to receive either DVR or placebo; rings were replaced
122 every 4 weeks. HIV-infection status was determined by testing for seroconversion
123 every 4 weeks. Ring use was stopped at the visit when seroconversion was
124 detected, and a follow-up Exit visit was held six weeks later. After primary analysis,
125 the trial continued in double-blind fashion until efficacy results were known,
126 whereafter all enrolled participants received open-label DVR until implementation of
127 the extension trial IPM 032 (DREAM). The current virologic analysis extends the
128 primary analysis to include all participants from the primary analysis, those who
129 seroconverted during The Ring-Study open-label period, those with HIV-1 RNA at
130 the last DVR use visit and seroconversion at the Exit visit and those who
131 discontinued early with detectable HIV-1 RNA.

132

133 DREAM was an open-label extension of The Ring Study for participants who had
134 remained HIV-negative during The Ring Study (8). Participants received open-label
135 DVR and attended a 1-month follow-up visit and could either proceed with visits once
136 every 3 months or attend monthly visits up to Month 3 followed by visits once every 3
137 months, when they were tested for seroconversion.

138

139 Plasma samples were stored for HIV-1 resistance testing at each visit.

140

141 Stored plasma from seroconversions in both trials were tested retrospectively in
142 reverse sequential order for HIV-1 RNA using the Abbott RealTime HIV-1
143 Amplification Reagent Kit to estimate the time of infection more accurately.

144

145 The trials were registered with ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT01539226 and NCT02862171)
146 and conducted in compliance with the International Council for Harmonisation of
147 Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use guidelines and other
148 applicable local regulatory requirements. The trial protocols were approved by
149 independent ethics committees at all research centres as previously described (3, 8).
150 All participants provided written informed consent before trial-related procedures
151 were initiated.

152

153 ***Seroconversion Assessment***

154 Seroconversion was assessed using rapid HIV-1 test kits and confirmed with
155 Western blotting (Bio-Rad Genetic Systems™ HIV-1 Western blot) and HIV-1 RNA
156 detection using PCR as described previously (3, 8).

157

158 ***Population-based Genotyping***

159 Partial or full-length reverse transcriptase (RT) sequencing was performed at the
160 Bio-Analytical Research Corporation Laboratory in South Africa (BARC-SA) (9). All
161 plasma samples with HIV-1 RNA >200 copies/mL collected during The Ring Study
162 and DREAM were tested. Ninety-five percent of The Ring Study sequencing was of
163 >326 codons; 76% were full-length. The DREAM trial analysis used full-length
164 sequencing. The comparator reference sequence was the Stanford consensus
165 subtype B (<https://hivdb.stanford.edu/page/release-notes/>, accessed 28 June 2022).

166

167 ***Next Generation Sequencing***

168 The NGS assay was performed at the Microbicide Trials Network (MTN) Virology
169 Core Laboratory, Pittsburgh, using Illumina platform-based sequencing of RT codons
170 81 – 149 and 152 – 212 of the HIV-1 RT encoding-region to identify known HIV-1
171 RAMs. Unique molecular identifiers (UMI) on RT-PCR primers allowed consensus-
172 sequence characterization as described previously (10). Sensitivity could be
173 calculated for each analysis and were classified as 95% confidence to detect 1%
174 (UMI ≥ 298), 5% (UMI ≥ 58) or 10% (UMI ≥ 28) sensitivity. The comparator reference
175 sequence was HIV-1_{HXB2}.

176

177 ***Genotypic Susceptibility Analysis***

178 HIV-1 RT RAMs were identified using the Stanford HIVdb algorithm, Version 8.4,
179 which was used to obtain genotypic susceptibility scores (GSS) and drug resistance
180 interpretations for the NNRTIs approved for therapeutic use at the time of the trial
181 (efavirenz, etravirine, nevirapine, and rilpivirine) (11, 12).

182

183 ***Phenotypic Susceptibility***

184 Phenotypic susceptibility on plasma-derived HIV-1 was performed at the MTN
185 Virology Core Laboratory, Pittsburgh, using a validated laboratory-developed TZM-bl
186 luciferase-based single cycle assay as previously described (10). Fold-change (FC)
187 was determined by dividing the viral IC₅₀ by wild-type reference values.

188

189 ***Adherence to product use***

190 Adherence was assessed as described previously (3).

191

192 ***Statistical Analysis***

193 Descriptive statistics were used in the main. Apparent imbalances in proportions
194 between groups were evaluated using Fisher's Exact Test, at a significance level of
195 5%.

196

197 **Results**

198 During The Ring Study, including the open-label stage, 148 of 1959 participants
199 became infected with HIV-1 during DVR use (double-blind: DVR: 82/1299, 6.3%;
200 placebo: 61/649, 9.4%; open-label DVR: 5/345, 1.4%) (Figure 1). Baseline
201 demographic characteristics were similar between seroconversions in the two groups
202 (Table S1). Most infections were categorized as HIV-1 subtype C (HIV-1 subtype:
203 DVR, placebo: C: 88.5%, 88.5%; A: 2.3%, 3.3%; D: 3.4%, 1.6%;
204 missing/unassigned: 5.7%, 6.6%).

205

206 ***Viral Characterization at Seroconversion***

207 Most participants from The Ring Study had NNRTI RAM-free virus at seroconversion
208 using population-based sequencing, distributed equally between groups (DVR:
209 71/84, 84.5%; placebo: 50/58, 86.2%). Of those with NNRTI RAMs, most had single
210 mutations (Table 1). All NNRTI RAMs observed in the DVR group (A98G, K101E,
211 K103N and E138A) were also found in the placebo group. Only one mutation,
212 E138A, was more prevalent in the DVR-treated group but the difference was not
213 statistically significant (E138A: DVR: 9/84, 10.7%; placebo: 2/58, 3.4%, $P=0.20$,
214 Fisher's Exact Test). One additional instance of E138A was observed in a DVR
215 seroconversion at the Exit visit but the analysis at the seroconversion time point had
216 failed. Major mutations associated with resistance to NRTIs or protease inhibitors
217 were not observed. A correlation between the presence or absence of NNRTI RAMs
218 and dapivirine residual levels and plasma concentrations was not found (Table S2).
219
220 Analysis of other mutations, including changes observed during in vitro passage with
221 dapivirine (5, 6) and those in the Stanford HIVdb algorithm 8.4 that were non-scoring

222 (Supplementary information), detected only V90I (DVR: 1/84; placebo: 4/58), A98S
223 (DVR: 2/84; placebo: 1/58), K101R (DVR: 2/84; placebo: 0/58) and V179I (DVR:
224 5/84; placebo: 2/58).

225

226 ***Longitudinal Population-based Genotyping Analysis***

227 Population-based genotyping paired analyses before and at seroconversion were
228 available for participants with HIV-1 RNA detectable before seroconversion (DVR:
229 n=52; placebo: n=26); missing pairs were due mostly to seroconversion coinciding
230 with first HIV-1 RNA detection. Paired samples were separated on average by 35
231 and 31 days, respectively. Selection of NNRTI RAMs was not observed between
232 time points.

233

234 Paired samples from seroconversion and Exit visits were also analyzed (DVR: n=63;
235 placebo: n=41); missing values were due mainly to discontinuation without an Exit
236 visit. The samples were separated on average by 47 and 53 days for the DVR and
237 placebo groups, respectively. NNRTI RAMs were first detected at the Exit Visit in two
238 DVR-group viruses (G190G/A and K103K/N with V106V/M). Both participants had
239 high viral load ($>10^6$ copies/mL) at the first detection of HIV-1 RNA, 34 and 28 days
240 prior to seroconversion; however, at seroconversion, HIV-1 RNA concentrations
241 were much reduced (>85 -fold and 23-fold, respectively). In both instances, the last
242 recorded ring residual and plasma dapivirine concentrations (ring-residual dapivirine:
243 20.6 mg and 22.3 mg; plasma concentrations: 219 and 241 pg/mL, respectively)
244 were not notably different from the mean values of the group without resistance (see
245 Table S2).

246

247 ***Next Generation Sequencing at Seroconversion***

248 Of 101 available samples, 57 (100%) DVR and 41 (93.2%) placebo group viruses
249 were successfully analyzed using NGS to detect 10% minority species, most with
250 sensitivity to detect a 1% minority species with 95% confidence (DVR: 48/57, 84.2%;
251 placebo: 41/44, 93.2%). NNRTI RAMs were observed in 16 instances (DVR: 9/57,
252 15.8%; placebo: 7/41, 17.1%). There were only two viruses with NNRTI RAMs that
253 were additional to those detected using population-based genotyping, one from each
254 group (Table 2). In the DVR group, one participant had 5% prevalence of virus with
255 G190A, which was also detected later using population-based genotyping at the Exit
256 visit (Table 2, participant D7). The other participant with minority species was from
257 the placebo group (G190A: 2%; G190E: 2%) (Table 2, participant P6).

258

259 All NNRTI RAMs detected using both population-based genotyping and NGS were
260 present at 99% – 100%. Minority species were detected infrequently.

261

262 ***Genotypic and Phenotypic Susceptibility at Seroconversion***

263 Dapivirine phenotypic susceptibility was determined for all viruses with known NNRTI
264 RAMs, while susceptibility to other NNRTIs, efavirenz, etravirine, nevirapine and
265 rilpivirine, was determined for viruses with E138A (Table 1). The FC range for
266 susceptibility to dapivirine was 1.3 – 5.1 FC relative to wild-type virus (wild-type viral
267 susceptibility: geometric mean IC_{50} : 0.44 nM; range 0.23 – 0.86 nM). The lowest FC
268 was associated with a virus encoding an E138A mutation and the greatest FC was
269 found with the dual-mutant virus K101E, E138A. Susceptibility tended to be reduced
270 similarly in the placebo group (geometric mean FC 5.8, range 0.9 – 120), which
271 included two outlier viruses with FC 24.8 and 120 (Table 1).

272

273 Susceptibility to efavirenz, etravirine, nevirapine and rilpivirine was measured in
274 viruses with E138A alone (n=8), the geometric mean FC relative to wild-type viruses
275 (wild-type virus geometric mean IC₅₀: efavirenz: 0.43 nM; etravirine: 0.72 nM;
276 nevirapine: 28 nM; and rilpivirine: 0.18 nM) was in the range 1.12 – 1.85. The
277 greatest FC for a virus with E138A as the only NNRTI RAM was with nevirapine
278 (2.9 FC) (Table S3). The dual mutant (K101E, E138A) showed FC in the range 2.40
279 (rilpivirine) to 5.30 (nevirapine). In the DVR group, genotypic susceptibility was
280 mainly in the range “susceptible” to “low-level resistant”. High-level resistance was
281 predicted to efavirenz and nevirapine with K103N (DVR: 2/82, 2.4%; placebo: 1/57,
282 1.8%). In addition, K101E/E138A (1/82, 1.2%) predicted intermediate resistance to
283 nevirapine and high-level resistance to rilpivirine (Table S3).

284

285 ***DREAM Trial***

286 In the DREAM trial, 18 of 941 (1.9%) enrolled participants experienced
287 seroconversion while using the DVR, one of whom had insufficient HIV-1 RNA
288 (≤ 40 copies/mL) for analysis. Virus from five participants (5/17; 29.4%) was found
289 with single NNRTI RAMs (A98G, K101E, E138A and two with K103N). Analysis of
290 pre-seroconversion samples was limited, given visits were 3 months apart. There
291 were four paired samples on treatment; one showed the emergence of an NNRTI
292 RAM (K103N) between 99 and 192 days after the first detection of HIV-1 RNA. In
293 this instance, there was a high initial viral load (1,367,100 copies/mL) followed by a
294 45-fold reduction at the time of K103N detection (29,955 copies/mL). Of 15 paired
295 samples from seroconversion and Exit visits, new mutations were not observed.

296

297 Sixteen of the 18 participants had NGS analysis performed successfully. Only one
298 participant was found with a minority viral species not observed using population-
299 based genotyping (2% prevalence of G190E with 100% A98G). Phenotypic analysis,
300 limited due to sample availability (n=5 including 2 mutant viruses, A98G and K103N),
301 did not reveal any susceptibility reduction to dapivirine, etravirine or rilpivirine, but the
302 virus with K103N showed susceptibility reduction to efavirenz (8.93 FC) and
303 nevirapine (41.1 FC) (Table S4).
304

305 **Discussion**

306 This extended analysis of viruses from seroconversion during DVR use supports
307 previous findings (3, 8). Overall, there was a low prevalence of virus with NNRTI
308 RAMs at seroconversion, with approximately 85% of viruses found to be wild-type in
309 both the DVR and placebo groups from The Ring Study and 71% in DREAM. During
310 the trials, efavirenz was the preferred first line antiretroviral drug (The Ring Study:
311 March 2012 - December 2016; DREAM: July 2016 - January 2019), and the
312 prevalence of NNRTI transmission surveillance mutations in Southern Africa was
313 rising at 23% per year (prevalence: 2010 – 2013: 2.9%; 2014 – 2016: 10.7%) (13).
314 Epidemiologic studies of HIV resistance generally use the WHO surveillance of
315 transmitted drug resistance mutation list (14), which excludes mutations at RT
316 codons 98 and 138. When the mutations at these codons are omitted from the
317 current analysis, the proportion of participants with resistant virus (The Ring Study:
318 DVR: 3/84, 3.6%; placebo 4/58, 6.9%; DREAM: 3/17, 17.6%) is consistent with the
319 reported community prevalence at the time of the trials (13). The NNRTI RAMs
320 observed in virus from the DVR groups were also found in the placebo group and
321 there were no additional genotypic signals of dapivirine-mediated resistance. Indeed,
322 the lack of any Y181C among viruses after DVR use is an important finding as this
323 mutation was frequently observed during in vitro passage with dapivirine (6, 7).

324

325 The polymorphism E138A was numerically more prevalent in the DVR group, but the
326 difference from placebo was not statistically significant. Furthermore, a similar
327 Phase III trial with DVR, MTN-020 (ASPIRE), did not find any imbalance (E138A:
328 DVR: 4.4%; placebo: 5.2%) (10). The E138A mutation is more common in subtype C
329 virus than in subtype B (15), particularly among efavirenz or nevirapine failures (16)

330 and can be self-maintained in clusters of untreated people with HIV (17, 18), so the
331 observed prevalence of E138A with DVR was within the expected range for this
332 population.

333

334 Unfortunately, transmitted viral genotypes cannot be obtained at the exact time of
335 infection; however, during early infection the virus retains low genetic diversity due to
336 the transmission bottleneck. Infection seeding with single virions in approximately
337 76% – 90% of infections was reported for women in sub-Saharan Africa (19). This
338 predicts that infecting virus is likely to be highly homogeneous. The retrospective
339 NGS analysis at seroconversion, although limited, confirmed homogeneity of
340 mutations (100 – 99%) in most instances, consistent with mutations arising from
341 recent transmission (20). Only two samples from The Ring Study (one in each
342 treatment group) and one from DREAM had variants not found using population-
343 based genotyping. All three had minority mutations at RT codon 190 (The Ring
344 Study: DVR: G190A; placebo: G190A and G190E; DREAM: G190E). The DVR
345 participant from The Ring Study had virus with G190G/A detected at the post-
346 treatment follow-up visit using population-based genotyping. Notably, G190A is not
347 associated with reduced susceptibility to dapivirine (5, 21) and has not been selected
348 during in vitro passage with dapivirine (5, 6).

349

350 The genotypes generally harbored only one NNRTI RAM, indicating a lack of
351 development of resistance pathways between infection and seroconversion. In the
352 analysis of phenotypic susceptibility of viruses with NNRTI RAMs, either no reduction
353 or only a modest reduction in susceptibility to dapivirine was observed, and FC
354 values were generally similar to those in the placebo group, although findings in the

355 placebo group included two viruses with high-level resistance. In addition, consistent
356 with genotypic susceptibility interpretation, most viruses with NNRTI RAMs from
357 participants in the DVR group retained susceptibility to other NNRTIs. The virus
358 showing the greatest reduction in susceptibility in the DVR group of The Ring Study
359 (5.1 FC) had two NNRTI RAMs (K101E, E138A). Similarly, the two viruses with high-
360 level resistance from the placebo group had more than one mutation.

361

362 The assertion that because systemic exposure to dapivirine is low during ring use it
363 does not promote NNRTI RAM selection (22), was further supported by the
364 longitudinal evaluation of virus when selection of new resistance mutations was not
365 found between HIV-1 RNA detection and seroconversion in The Ring Study. The
366 mechanism for new mutation appearance in the two instances after stopping DVR
367 use (The Ring Study) and one on-treatment (DREAM) is unclear. The specific
368 mutations (K103N, V106M and G190A) were among the most prevalent NNRTI
369 RAMs in infections before and after antiretroviral treatment in areas of South Africa
370 (23, 24). However, in vitro, while K103N was observed in one dapivirine-passage
371 experiment with a subtype B virus, G190A and V106M were never selected by
372 dapivirine in vitro. Indeed, the most common mutation observed in vitro was Y181C
373 (6, 7), which was not found among clinical samples. Furthermore, in site-directed
374 mutant virus, G190A and V106M are not associated with resistance to dapivirine
375 (1 – 2 FC) and K103N is associated with low-level resistance (5 FC), while Y181C is
376 associated with intermediate resistance (8 FC) (data on file). Of note, the first
377 detection at the Exit visit of G190A and K103N/V106M, and the detection of K103N
378 during DREAM after an initial wild-type observation, were all accompanied by large
379 viral load reductions (23 – >85-fold). As the DVR does not deliver systemic antiviral

380 concentrations of dapivirine (3), viral load reduction early in infection was likely due
381 to immune activation. Therefore, while de novo resistance selection cannot be
382 excluded, selective immune-based activity against wild-type virus in a mixed
383 infection presents a potential alternate mechanism to dapivirine-mediated resistance
384 selection.

385

386 Overall, virologic findings were similar between the placebo and DVR cohorts,
387 except for the numeric E138A-prevalence difference. The mutations observed are
388 consistent with what we expect to see for transmitted resistance in this geographic
389 region. In contrast, the mutational profiles were not expected based on in vitro
390 dapivirine characteristics, supporting transmission as the key mechanism for NNRTI
391 RAM presence. Furthermore, susceptibility to future treatment options was largely
392 retained.

393

394 **Data Sharing**

395 De-identified individual participant data from The Ring Study and DREAM will be
396 available to researchers with a methodologically sound proposal. Data requestors
397 will need to sign a data access agreement. Publication concept proposal forms
398 should be directed to mconradie@ipmglobal.org to gain access.

399

400

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409

410 **Conflict of Interests**

411 John Steytler, Jeremy Nuttall and Neliëtte van Niekerk were at the time of conduct of
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416

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503 **Figure 1. Overview of Randomization, Outcomes and Virology Data Availability**
 504 **at the Seroconversion Time Point for The Ring Study**

505

506 DVR = dapivirine vaginal ring

507 ¹ Participants were given the option to enter an open-label phase when the
 508 randomized part of the trial was ended. Participants and investigators remained
 509 blinded to the randomized treatment.

510 ² All available samples at the seroconversion time point were submitted for this
 511 retrospective analysis.

512 ³ Viruses with NNRTI RAMs were all assessed retrospectively for dapivirine
 513 susceptibility; for other NNRTIs, susceptibility was assessed only for viruses
 514 encoding E138A.

Table 1. Mutations and Dapivirine Susceptibility in Virus from Participants at Seroconversion on The Ring Study

NNRTI RAMs	Population-based Genotype n (%)		Dapivirine Susceptibility FC ^{a, b} Geometric Mean (SD) [Range]		Genotypic Susceptibility Determination			
	DVR (N=84)	Placebo (N=58)	DVR	Placebo	EFV	ETR	NVP	RPV
The Ring Study								
None	71 (84.5)	50 (86.2)	N/A	N/A	S	S	S	S
Any	13 (15.9)	8 (13.8)	3.1 (1.6) [1.3–5.1]	5.8 (5.3) [0.9–120]	—	—	—	—
A98G	2 (2.4)	1 (1.7)	4.1 ^c	2.5	LLR	PLLR	IR	LLR
K101E	0	1 (1.7)	—	4.2	LLR	LLR	IR	IR
K103N	2 (2.4)	1 (1.7)	2.0 ^c	3.5	HLR	S	HLR	S
E138A	8 (9.8) ^d	2 (3.4)	2.9 (1.6) [1.3–5.0]	0.9 ^c	S	PLLR	S	LLR
K101E, E138A	1 (1.2)	0	5.1	—	LLR	LLR	IR	HLR
E138Q	0	1 (1.7)	—	2.2	PLLR	PLLR	PLLR	LLR
V106M, Y188C	0	1 (1.7)	—	24.8	HLR	S	HLR	S
V108I, Y181C, H221Y	0	1 (1.7)	—	120	IR	IR	HLP	HLR

DVR = dapivirine vaginal ring; EFV = efavirenz; ETR = etravirine; NVP = nevirapine; RPV = rilpivirine; IR = intermediate resistance; HLR = high-level resistance; LLR = low-level resistance; PLLR = potential low-level resistance; S = susceptible; FC = fold-change (relative to wild-type viruses)

^a Three independent assays were performed for each virus.

^b Fold-changes were calculated using geometric mean values from 10 contemporary wild-type viruses.

^c There were 3 missing values (DVR: A98G and K103N; placebo: E138A).

^d One additional virus with E138A was observed at the Exit visit in a participant without successful sequencing at seroconversion.

Table 2. NNRTI RAMs Observed using Population-based Genotyping and NGS Genotype^a at HIV-1 Seroconversion by Individual Participants

Participant Number	Population-based Genotype	NGS Genotype (% NNRTI RAM; Sensitivity)
Dapivirine Vaginal Ring		
D 1	K103N	K103N (100%; 1%)
D 2	E138A	E138A (100%; 1%)
D 3	E138A	E138A (100%; 1%)
D 4	E138A	E138A (100%; 1%)
D 5	E138A	E138A (100%; 1%)
D 6	E138A	E138A (100%; 1%)
D 7	Wild-type	G190A (5%; 1%)
D 8	A98G	A98G (99%; 1%)
D 9	E138A	E138A (100%; 1%)
Placebo Ring		
P 1	K103N	K103N (100%; 1%)
P 2	A98G	A98G (99%; 1%)
P 3	K101E	K101E (100%; 1%)
P 4	V106M, Y188C	V106M, Y188C (100%; 1%)
P 5	V108I, Y181C, H221Y ^b	V108I, Y181C (100%; 10%)
P 6	Wild-type	G190A, G190E (each 2%; 10%)
P 7	E138Q	E138Q (100%; 1%)
<p>HIV-1 = human immunodeficiency virus type 1; NGS = next generation sequencing; NNRTI = non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor; RNA = ribonucleic acid</p> <p>^a NGS sensitivity to detect at least a 10% minority species.</p> <p>^b H221Y was outside the area sequenced with the NGS assay used.</p>		